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D3.1

Use Case Work Plans

WP3
Community, Support and Use Cases

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Executive Summary

This document introduces and provides detailed work plans for the four BioExcel-2 Pilot Use Cases that are being undertaken within WP3, namely:

Use Case 1: Antibody Design

Use Case 2: High-throughput Modelling of Interactomes

Use Case 3: Rational Drug Design

Use Case 4: Electronic Interaction Phenomena

The Use Cases serve as a focal point driving the development of software and workflows in WP1 & WP2 and as a demonstrator to the wider community of relevant researchers from academia and industry of what can be done with the software and expertise developed within the BioExcel Centre of Excellence.

The work plan for each Use Case consists of a number of concrete activities. These are described in detail including with a planned timeline and with milestones that serve as criteria against which progress can be evaluated on an ongoing basis. Expected impacts on future users arising from the Use Case activities are stated. Interdependencies are mapped out between various Use Case activities as well as between the Use Case activities and the code and workflow development work taking place in WP1 and WP2 as well as other factors internal and external to the BioExcel-2 project as a whole.

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Introduction

The four BioExcel Pilot Use Cases were selected to reflect a range of concrete problems of interest to the wider academic and industrial communities. BioExcel seeks to engage with. They act as focal points for the project as a whole by bringing together and driving many of the BioExcel activities including development of the BioExcel core applications and workflows as well as in-depth support and training. The Use Cases are ambitious because they serve as key targets to ensure maximum impact from BioExcel's work to develop biomolecular modelling software and expertise in its usage, to address important challenges in the life sciences and to have an impact on concrete application usage at scale. The Use Cases will serve as demonstrators of what can be achieved using BioExcel software and expertise and provide well-documented, best-practice examples of how to solve difficult problems using large-scale computing resources. They will help us to understand and address the current needs of end users and provide extensible templates for future research, as well as good starting points for training in modern Life Science HPC usage.

The Use Cases combine core BioExcel applications and software-enabled workflows and rely on the collaborative application and further development of expertise by multiple project partners, as well as engaging actively with project-external colleagues in academia and industry.

This document formulates work plans for the Use Cases. The work plans describe the key activities that are planned to be undertaken by the contributing partners within each Use Case, including details regarding expected staff effort from the various partners and a timeline, the software involved, outputs, risks, expected impact on users, etc. The work plans also map out interdependencies between the different Use Case activities, other activities within the project such as code (WP1) and workflow (WP2) development, and factors external to the project.

It should be noted that as stated in the BioExcel-2 proposal, the Use Cases are research activities aimed at showcasing BioExcel capabilities in the context of real-world challenges and are expected to evolve in response to user and community needs as well as project-internal software and workflow developments. For these reasons their scope will be reviewed on a yearly basis. Nonetheless the work plans detailed here are essential and form the basis for planning and execution of the Use Case work and will serve as a reference point to evaluate progress as the project progresses. Data management plans for the use cases are described in a separate concurrent deliverable (D3.2).

The work plan for each Use Case consists of multiple activities, with each activity detailed in a table following the template given on the following page.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Work plan activity template

Name of activity	
ID	
Software involved	
Description	
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected PM for completion	
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	
Impact on another Use Case activity?	
Dependencies on WP1 work?	
Impact on WP1 work?	
Dependencies on WP2 work?	
Impact on WP2 work?	
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	
Impact on future users	
Background material/links	
Partner responsible for planning	
Partner responsible for executing	
Other partners involved	
Estimated required effort (in PM)	
Estimated start month	
Estimated end month	
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	

Use Case 1: Antibody Design

Description

One of the fastest growing branches in the pharmaceutical industry is drug design based on antibodies, with antibody (Ab) fragments already proving to be an important class of therapeutics, overtaking small molecule drugs from synthetic chemistry. These macromolecular pharmaceuticals give extremely high specificity and the ability to use the body's own immune system to eliminate diseased tissue e.g. tumors, but their computational design is challenging due to their size and complexity.

Key challenges are:

- to reliably predict 3D structures of antibodies, in particular the Complementarity-Determining Regions (CDRs)
- to model their binding mode and understand how structure and dynamics are altered in this process
- to predict improved binding affinity through systematic amino acid mutations

This Use Case aims to address all these challenges through an integrative approach combining the core BioExcel software comprising of GROMACS, HADDOCK and PMX, and with the development of computational workflows to facilitate usability and execution on Exascale high-performance computing resources.

This Use Case is expected to be of particular interest to the pharma industry. BioExcel already has established contacts with several companies involved in antibody design who are using BioExcel core software and who stand to benefit from this Use Case, and to achieve maximum impact we are eager to ensure that work done is informed by concrete cases of interest to industry.

We will use GROMACS to improve antibody 3D structures and accurately sample multiple alternative predictions of conformation. The resulting conformations will be used as input in HADDOCK to model the interaction with its target antigen. The modelling of the complex using HADDOCK will be guided by a variety of experimental and predicted data. Models of the complexes will be optimized by MD using GROMACS to select a final model as input for antibody engineering using PMX to improve its binding affinity.

The designed antibodies from the HADDOCK/GROMACS pipeline will be further subjected to the single point mutation analysis by means of molecular dynamics based free energy calculations run by the PMX team. At this step a large-scale high-accuracy computational scan of amino acid mutations will be performed aimed at increasing antibody-antigen binding affinity. The procedure will be iterated if needed to identify key residues responsible for the largest changes in the binding free energy.

Summary of Work Plan Activities

ID	Name	Partner	Effort (PM)	Est. start month	Est. end month
A1.1	Prepare antibody/antigen model for all-atom simulation	KTH	0.5	5	7
A1.2	Initial sampling of antibody conformations before docking	KTH	0.5	6	9
A1.3	Employ advanced sampling schemes for sampling of antibody conformations before docking	KTH	2.5	9	24
A1.4	Refinement of statically modelled antibody/antigen interactions through Molecular Dynamics simulation	KTH	2.5	10	28
A1.5	Automate and document molecular dynamics simulation setup, production run and analysis	KTH	1	6	28
A1.6	Benchmarking alchemical free energy calculations for antibody-antigen stabilization	MPG	3	6	18
A1.7	Optimizing antibody-antigen interactions by alchemical free energy calculations after docking and MD sampling	MPG	3	6	36
A1.8	Defining the baseline performance of HADDOCK for antibody-antigen modelling under different scenarios	UU	6	-6	4
A1.9	Improved modelling of antibody-antigen modelling by using antibody conformations sampled by MD	UU	6	9	30
A1.10	Demonstration of antibody-antigen modelling on real experimental data	UU	3	24	36

Use Case 2: High-throughput Modelling of Interactomes

Description

The human genome has revealed over 20,000 expressed proteins, known as the proteome, which are the workhorses of human life and perform all manner of critical cellular functions. These proteins, however, do not work in isolation, but by interaction with each other and with other biomolecules, thereby forming a complex network of interactions known as the interactome. This intricate network consists of all interactions involving hundreds of thousands of protein-protein and other biomolecular complexes. Irregularities in the functioning of the interactome, e.g. through environment-induced miscommunication or mutation-induced alterations to the proteome are responsible for many diseases, which is why it is important to understand how the interactome works at the atomic level.

There are two main challenges associated with understanding the interactome:

- Adding the structural dimension to possibly hundreds of thousands of interactions between protein-protein and other biomolecular complexes
- Predicting what the interactome (the network) looks like given the knowledge of the proteome (the building blocks of the network), which requires predicting the affinity of the complexes involved

The first challenge will require running massive amounts of independent docking runs in parallel, all generating large numbers of files. The second challenge will require all-vs-all docking of the network components and prediction of their binding affinity, e.g. using parallel molecular dynamics simulation. Doing so in an efficient manner and achieving the Use Case goals will require efficient usage of high-throughput (HTC) and high-performance computing (HPC) including on Exascale resources, and efficiently handling and analysing large amounts of data.

These challenges will not be met exclusively by using HTC resources through the HADDOCK portal. We intend to modularize HADDOCK to decouple pre- and post-processing steps from the bulk of the computing to allow for the development of custom and efficient workflows that can be executed on HPC resources for the purpose of Exascale modelling of interactomes.

Both challenges will also benefit from current advances in AI and deep learning approaches for identification of near-native models from a large pool (e.g. from docking or other modelling methods) and the prediction of the binding affinity of those complexes.

Developments related to this Use Case are expected to benefit the antibody-antigen modelling Use Case (Use Case 1) in addition to the wider interaction modelling research community. Containerization of workflow modules is expected to facilitate deployment on HTC and HPC resources and on the in-house computational infrastructure of pharma companies.

Summary of Work Plan Activities

ID	Name	Partner	Effort (PM)	Est. start month	Est. end month
A2.1	Reliability analysis of protein-protein interaction energy prediction through all-atom molecular dynamics simulation	KTH	0.5	9	11
A2.2	Distinguishing native from non-native docking models by MD	UU	4	5	24
A2.3	Investigating suitable mechanism of launching a large number of docking simulations as single job on HPC resources	UU	2	6	10
A2.4	Optimize the identification of near-native docking models using machine learning methods	UU	4	9	21

Use Case 3: Rational Drug Design

Description

Rational drug design refers to the informed design of small drug molecules so that bind with high affinity to a target protein. It relies on prior knowledge of the structure, function, and mechanism of the protein target, thereby reducing or avoiding the random testing of millions of small molecules. This usually involves the following steps: (i) Protein target and hit identification (target-to-hit phase), (ii) gaining further knowledge on the target structure and function as well as working on several chemical series in parallel (hit-to-lead phase), and (iii) optimizing the chemical lead structure(s) in terms of interactions with the target and other properties such as ADME and selectivity (lead optimization).

The interest in this method has been boosted by advances in various fields such as computer science, molecular biology, biophysics, biochemistry, data science and statistics. Among these, computational chemistry methods have had a positive impact on generating new insights for medicinal chemists. Structure-based drug design practitioners work in close collaboration with medicinal chemists commonly for lead identification and optimization. Iterative rounds of structure-based design, synthesis, and experimental testing provide an increasingly clear picture of structure-activity relationships with respect to the target interactions and drug metabolism. With the advent of machine learning, and particularly deep learning, high-dimensional data and complex systems can be harnessed for drug discovery and design.

BioExcel's rational drug design use case unites several high impact computer-aided drug design techniques in biomolecular workflows that are relevant to the pharmaceutical industry. We have divided the use case into four different studies of increasing complexity that each have a dedicated workflow (WF):

- **WF1: Moving mutational analysis into the structural field for drug design**
- **WF2: Tackling mutations inactivating tumor suppressors**
- **WF3: Quantitative predictions of binding affinity in lead optimization**
- **WF4: Machine learning for efficient drug design**

Our role in BioExcel

BioExcel is working on providing the necessary software modules and workflows to achieve the automation of biomolecular pipelines. The virtual screening (VS) workflow that was developed in the first phase of the project is a cornerstone of all the suggested workflows. The library used for the assembly of this particular pipeline allows its usage in different computational architectures, including High Performance Computing (HPC) supercomputers. Millions of compounds can be scanned in a single run due to efficient massive parallel execution.

Our collaborators and the use case context

Nostrum Biodiscovery (<http://www.nostrumbiodiscovery.com/>) is a spin-off company of the BSC with a large expertise in structure-based drug design applied to pharmaceutically relevant early drug discovery projects.

The Computational Biomolecular Dynamics group at the Max Planck Institute for Biophysical Chemistry (<https://www.mpibpc.mpg.de/degroot>) studies the relationship between the dynamics and function of biological macromolecules at the atomic level using computer simulations. The software pmx is helpful in automatically setting up topologies for free energy calculations and has the potential to significantly impact lead optimization.

Particular interest of the use case for BioExcel

Ambitious pipelines like the ones presented in this use case will exploit the power of the BioExcel building blocks library, combining a molecular dynamics (MD) program (GROMACS), with free energy setups (pmx), docking (Autodock), and High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA, i.e. prediction algorithms, e.g. PMUT). The four proposed workflows can be customized to address the needs of pharmaceutical companies, which can largely benefit from the CoE's expertise.

Summary of Work Plan Activities

ID	Name	Partner	Effort (PM)	Est. start month	Est. end month
A3.1	Cancer mutations filtering & identification of pathological mutations	BSC	4	6	18
A3.2	Conformational ensembles from protein variants	IRB	4	6	18
A3.3	Conformational ensembles from small molecules	IRB	4	6	24
A3.4	Ensemble Docking	IRB	5	6	18
A3.5	Alchemical free energy calculations of relative ligand binding free energy differences	NBD / MPG	6	6	36
A3.6	Molecular Dynamics trajectories analyses	IRB	4	6	36
A3.7	Molecular Dynamics trajectories storage	IRB	4	6	36
A3.8	Peptide Mutational Scans	NBD	4	18	36
A3.9	High Performance Data Analytics	BSC	5	18	36
A3.10	Enabling advanced use of GROMACS, improve usability & implement advanced functionality within the use case	KTH	4	6	36

Use Case 4: Electronic Interaction Phenomena

Description

This use Case involves two sub-cases, one involving Proton Dynamics and another Fluorescent Proteins, which are related by their use of hybrid QM/MM modelling and simulation approaches and the software used. The software packages involved here are GROMACS, CP2K, CPMD, MiMiC, and pmx.

Proton Dynamics

Mass spectrometry has revolutionized proteomics, i.e. the investigation of the myriad of protein/protein interactions in the cell. By using a very small sample content of proteins (usually in the micromolar concentration), a powerful implementation of the technique, so-called ionization/ion mobility mass spectrometry (ESI/IM-MS), can measure stoichiometry, shape and subunit architecture of protein and protein complexes in the gas phase.

The key assumption in the ESI/IM-MS technique is that the rearrangement of biomolecular units on passing from solution to gas phase is minimal. However, proton transfer phenomena may significantly affect structural properties, therefore understanding the mechanisms and quantifying the extent of these configurational changes will allow significant improvement in the predictions of this already powerful experimental technique.

We will use massively parallel hybrid QM/MM simulations to address this problem on an important example use case system: the protein beta-lactoglobulin. In particular, we will employ both the already developed MiMiC interface (which couples the ab-initio quantum molecular dynamics code CPMD to GROMACS), as well as the novel QM/MM interface between GROMACS and CP2K that is going to be developed by BioExcel. Comparison with the available experimental data will allow us to establish the accuracy of the methods used. This Use Case will illustrate parallel computational scaling, performance, and efficiency of unprecedented large-scale predictions using BioExcel's newly developed high performance computing approaches to study a highly relevant biological problem

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Fluorescent Proteins

Reversibly fluorescent proteins have become a reliable resource to monitor cellular functions, gene expressions, protein-protein interactions, intra-cellular interactions in living systems and for understanding diseases and finding novel strategies to tackle them. After fusing the fluorescent protein to another protein using gene technology, the exact location of that protein can be determined by monitoring the fluorescence emitted by the photo-excited fluorescent protein with a normal fluorescence light microscope. Consequently, fluorescent proteins are used routinely to monitor various phenomena inside living cells, such as gene expression, protein dynamics, protein-protein interactions, intercellular transport, or biogenesis. Recent developments have even pushed the spatial resolution of this technique beyond the diffraction limit (Nobel Prize in Chemistry 2014). One strategy for achieving nanometer resolution in cells is to use reversibly photo-switchable fluorescent proteins (RSFPs), whose fluorescence can be turned on and off repeatedly with different wavelengths.

Current approaches available to achieve the full potential of fluorescent proteins rely on random mutagenesis in combination with screening. However this approach is not only time consuming, but also requires substantial resources, and is thus only affordable for few bio-imaging laboratories. Furthermore, because this approach does not provide physical insight into the process that is the target of the optimization, it is also very difficult to optimize more than one parameter simultaneously (e.g. absorption spectrum, emission spectrum, switching efficiency, fluorescence yield, protein stability). Our bottom-up approach for predicting the effects of mutations in fluorescent proteins is based on atomistic computer simulations that will provide atomistic insights into the effect of the protein environment on its thermo-stability (folding stability and dimerization stability). These use force field MD simulations, PMX and free-energy calculations, and the new QM/MM interface between GROMACS and CP2K to predict photochemical properties (absorption spectrum, emission spectrum, quantum yields of switching/fluorescence) of the fluorescent proteins. This Use Case will also demonstrate how large-scale computational resources can be used to perform biomolecular QM/MM simulations.

MD, PMX and free energy calculations will be validated for Green Fluorescent Protein (GFP) and its known mutants against known experimental crystal structure, thermal stability, oligomerization affinity, absorption spectra, emission spectra, and dimerization affinities reported in previous studies. The second validation test will validate the properties of hitherto unknown mutants in RsGreen0.7 (a variant of GFP). At the same time, project-external colleagues from the Dedecker Lab at the University of Leuven will express these mutants and measure their properties experimentally. While carrying out these critical blind prediction tests, we will convene regularly with this group to discuss results.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Bringing together experts with all required know-how of the experiments and a mechanistic understanding of fluorescent proteins is essential to rapidly identify problems or limitations of our software and simulations. Because testing and code development will go hand in hand at this stage, systematic errors in our implementation or parameters, including model chemistries, can still be corrected if needed.

Summary of Work Plan Activities

ID	Name	Partner	Effort (PM)	Est. start month	Est. end month
A4.1	Inquiring needs and document interface to apply forces from QM simulations during molecular dynamics simulation	KTH	1	10	22
A4.2	Prepare fluorescent proteins and mutants models for simulation	JYU	3	3	12
A4.3	Extensive sampling of fluorescent proteins conformations using classical molecular dynamics	JYU	6	6	24
A4.4	Free energy simulations of folding and dimerization of different fluorescent proteins mutants.	JYU	6	8	14
A4.5	Calculation of isomerization profiles of chromophores in protein environments	JYU	9	12	24
A4.6	Modelling of spectral properties of fluorescent proteins and their mutants	JYU	6	12	24
A4.7	Prepare the beta-lactoglobulin protein models for molecular dynamics simulations	JUELICH	3	13	15
A4.8	QM and QM/MM investigation of proton transport in beta-lactoglobulin protein by CPMD and MiMiC interface	JUELICH	0	16	24
A4.9	QM and QM/MM investigation of proton transport in beta-lactoglobulin protein by CP2K and CP2K/GROMACS QM/MM interface	JUELICH	7	25	36
A4.10	Supporting massively parallel QM/MM simulations of protein dynamics and fluorescent proteins	UEDIN	7	12	36

Detailed Work Plans

Use Case 1: Antibody Design

Name of activity	Prepare antibody/antigen model for all-atom simulation
ID	A1.1
Software involved	GROMACS pre-processing tools, model building tools
Description	Molecular dynamics simulations requires possibly extensive pre-processing, depending on the quality of the available structural information. Required steps are modeling of missing parts, solvation and system equilibration, as well as choice of force-field and simulation parameters.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Antibody is stable in a short equilibrium simulation
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	None
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	Depends on choice of antibody.
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Provides a starting point for modelling antibody/antigen interactions, or initial sampling of antibody/antigen conformations
Dependencies on WP1 work?	No dependencies
Impact on WP1 work?	Improving GROMACS pre-processing tools
Dependencies on WP2 work?	In a later stage, workflow tools may be used to automate this step as much as possible.
Impact on WP2 work?	None
Connections with any other project	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

tasks or activities?	
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	None
Impact on future users	This activity show-cases necessary steps to set up an MD simulation specifically for antibody systems. With the co-development of pre-processing tools and workflows, we expect the steps in this activity to be easier to handle and more transparently documented.
Background material/links	N.A.
Partner responsible for planning	KTH / Christian Blau
Partner responsible for executing	KTH / Christian Blau
Other partners involved	N.A.
Estimated required effort (in PM)	0.5
Estimated start month	5
Estimated end month	7
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Depending on the quality of the model information, structures might not be stable enough in simulation setup so that this activity may take longer than planned.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Initial sampling of antibody conformations before docking
ID	A1.2
Software involved	GROMACS
Description	Generate multiple initial configurations of antibody conformations before performing docking with standard molecular dynamics simulation protocol.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Multiple conformations of antibody are available.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	None
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A1.1
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Input for antibody/antigen interaction modelling
Dependencies on WP1 work?	GROMACS code development will improve efficiency of configurational sampling, as well as facilitate simulation setup.
Impact on WP1 work?	Bottlenecks in simulation setup will be used to inform GROMACS development.
Dependencies on WP2 work?	No strict dependency; in the future, this activity will largely benefit from better setup and documentation through workflows
Impact on WP2 work?	Provides a concrete setup that may serve as a testing environment for workflow environments
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	N.A.
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

companies, software not developed in the project)	
Impact on future users	Users will benefit from provided simulation protocols.
Background material/links	
Partner responsible for planning	KTH / Christian Blau
Partner responsible for executing	KTH / Christian Blau
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	0.5
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	9
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Unforeseen difficulties in simulation system setup might delay this activity. Inherent behaviour of the simulation system might make efficient sampling of multiple relevant configurations hard.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Employ advanced sampling schemes for sampling of antibody conformations before docking
ID	A1.3
Software involved	GROMACS
Description	Improve antibody/antigen interaction modelling, by generating most representative antibody structure ensembles with advanced sampling schemes.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Multiple conformations of antibody are available. This task will be revisited when more detailed knowledge about antibody conformations is needed to antibody/antigen interaction modelling
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	First structure ensemble is available. (PM 12)
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A1.2
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Input for antibody/antigen interaction modelling
Dependencies on WP1 work?	GROMACS code development will improve efficiency of configurational sampling, as well as facilitate simulation setup.
Impact on WP1 work?	Bottlenecks in simulation setup will be used to inform GROMACS development.
Dependencies on WP2 work?	No strict dependency; in the future, this activity will largely benefit from better setup and documentation through workflows
Impact on WP2 work?	Provides a concrete setup that may serve as a testing environment for workflow environments
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	N.A.
Dependencies on	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	
Impact on future users	Users will benefit from provided simulation protocols.
Background material/links	N.A.
Partner responsible for planning	KTH / Alessandra Villa, Berk Hess
Partner responsible for executing	KTH / Alessandra Villa, Berk Hess
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	2.5
Estimated start month	9
Estimated end month	24
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Inherent behaviour of the simulation system might make efficient sampling of multiple relevant configurations hard.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Refinement of statically modelled antibody/antigen interactions through Molecular Dynamics simulation
ID	A1.4
Software involved	GROMACS
Description	Modeled Antibody/antigen interactions will be refined with a series of molecular dynamics simulations of a representative set of antibody/antigen interactions. Simulations will be accompanied by analysis of the interaction patterns seen within the generated ensembles. Future iterations on this task will employ advanced molecular dynamics sampling methods.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Dynamic antibody/antigen interaction patterns are made available. Task may be revisited when refining and improving the suggested antibody/antigen interaction modeling pipeline
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	An interaction pattern is defined. (PM 14)
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	Modeling
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Input for antibody/antigen interaction modelling
Dependencies on WP1 work?	GROMACS code development will improve efficiency of configurational sampling, as well as facilitate simulation setup.
Impact on WP1 work?	Bottlenecks in simulation setup will be used to inform GROMACS development.
Dependencies on WP2 work?	No strict dependency; in the future, this activity will largely benefit from better setup and documentation through workflows
Impact on WP2 work?	Provides a concrete setup that may serve as a testing environment for workflow environments
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	None
Dependencies on project-externals	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

(e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	
Impact on future users	Users will benefit from provided simulation protocols.
Background material/links	N.A.
Partner responsible for planning	KTH / Alessandra Villa
Partner responsible for executing	KTH/ Alessandra Villa, Catherine Bergh
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	2.5
Estimated start month	10
Estimated end month	28
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Even with the best sampling methods and high-performance compute infrastructure, the gain in knowledge from dynamic interaction might turn out less useful than expected.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Automate and document molecular dynamics simulation setup, production run and analysis
ID	A1.5
Software involved	GROMACS
Description	Enabling automated simulation setup requires the automation of numerous micro-decisions. For this automation, especially with automated workflows in sight, researchers are required to carefully document the motivation for the decisions they take.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Simulation setup is automated and documented in a way so that an experienced researcher can reproduce the result from inputs.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	None
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	1.2 and 1.3
Impact on another Use Case activity?	1.2 and 1.3
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Refactoring of simulation pre-processing will aid this task.
Impact on WP1 work?	N.A.
Dependencies on WP2 work?	This task will use results from workflow development.
Impact on WP2 work?	Will feed back findings and outputs to WP2 to enable efficient workflow setup
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	None
Dependencies on project-externals	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

(e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	
Impact on future users	Users will benefit from automation tools for setting up their own simulations
Background material/links	N.A.
Partner responsible for planning	KTH / Alessandra Villa
Partner responsible for executing	KTH / Alessandra Villa
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	1
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	28
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Depending on the level of assumed experience of a researcher, required documentation may quickly become excessive. To allow the person executing the task to strike a good balance between automation, documentation and assumed background knowledge, we focus on documentation where decisions are use case specific and automation where protocols are generalizable.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Benchmarking alchemical free energy calculations for antibody-antigen stabilization
ID	A1.6
Software involved	GROMACS+pmx, Rosetta, FoldX
Description	For an efficient and accurate calculation of binding free energy changes in an antibody-antigen complex it is important to establish an optimal calculation protocol. The estimated free energy differences will be compared to those computed by the other state-of-the-art methods.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	The protocol will be made available from the publicly accessible pmx web server (http://pmx.mpibpc.mpg.de/) and as Supplementary Information accompanying any publications in scientific journals that emerge. Benchmark results associated with the protocol will also be published.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	None
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	None
Impact on another Use Case activity?	The benchmark results will show the accuracy that can be achieved with alchemical calculations.
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Automation of the non-equilibrium free energy calculation setup.
Impact on WP1 work?	New features in the pmx framework needed for this use case will be developed in WP1
Dependencies on WP2 work?	None
Impact on WP2 work?	The developed setup could become a module in a workflow developed in WP2.
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	One benchmark dataset already provided by Immunocore.
Impact on future users	The simulation protocol that will be made available will allow for convenient application by potential future users of the alchemical free energy calculations to antibody mutations. The benchmark results will inform the users on the achievable accuracy, which is likely to improve uptake.
Background material/links	N.A.
Partner responsible for planning	MPG / Vytautas Gapsys, Bert de Groot
Partner responsible for executing	MPG / Vytautas Gapsys
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	3
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	18
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	This benchmark study requires development and evaluation of the alchemical protocol for antibody mutations. The protocol is a natural extension of a standard amino acid mutation workflow. The study requires datasets reporting on the antibody-antigen mutation free energy differences: a plethora of such datasets are readily published.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Optimizing antibody-antigen interactions by alchemical free energy calculations after docking and MD sampling.
ID	A1.7
Software involved	GROMACS+pmx
Description	Using a docked (HADDOCK) and refined (GROMACS) antibody-antigen model, single point mutations will be performed by means of alchemical simulations to optimize binding affinity of the antibody.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Mutations that enhance binding affinity of the antibody will be identified.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	None
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A1.4
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Comparison to the available data on affinities will allow evaluating the accuracy of the whole protocol: docking, refinement, free energy calculations.
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Automation of the non-equilibrium free energy calculation setup.
Impact on WP1 work?	New features in the pmx framework.
Dependencies on WP2 work?	None
Impact on WP2 work?	The developed setup could become a module in a workflow developed in WP2.
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	None
Dependencies on	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	
Impact on future users	The simulation protocol will be available to the users.
Background material/links	N.A.
Partner responsible for planning	MPG / Vytautas Gapsys, Bert de Groot
Partner responsible for executing	MPG / Vytautas Gapsys
Other partners involved	KTH, UU
Estimated required effort (in PM)	3
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	36
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	The accuracy of the free energy calculations highly depends on the starting models.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Defining the baseline performance of HADDOCK for antibody-antigen modelling under different scenarios
ID	A1.8
Software involved	HADDOCK
Description	<p>Benchmarking different scenarios for antibody-antigen docking with HADDOCK using the knowledge of the hypervariables loops on the antibody side and various levels of information on the antigen:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no information (i.e. entire surface) - loose definition of the epitope (e.g. residues within 10Å from antibody in reference complex) - accurate definition of the epitope (best case scenario - residues with 3.9Å of the antibody)
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Reported to EB in regular reporting and via a submitted manuscript
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	N.A.
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	None
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Docked models will feed into activities A1.4, A1.6 and A1.7
Dependencies on WP1 work?	None - current HADDOCK version supports already the scenarios investigated
Impact on WP1 work?	N.A.
Dependencies on WP2 work?	N.A.
Impact on WP2 work?	N.A.
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	Best practice coming out of this task should be documented in a antibody-antigen specific tutorial (related to WP3 activities)
Dependencies on project-externals	N.A.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

(e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	
Impact on future users	Optimized protocol for antibody-antigen modelling with HADDOCK depending on the amount of information available.
Background material/links	Use case description on BioExcel web site
Partner responsible for planning	Utrecht / Alexandre Bonvin, Zuzana Jandova
Partner responsible for executing	Utrecht / Zuzana Jandova
Other partners involved	N.A.
Estimated required effort (in PM)	6 PMs (5 of which not covered by BioExcel - work already done)
Estimated start month	-6 (the work was actually started by a PhD students not paid by BioExcel) prior to BioExcel-2 start, following submission of the project)
Estimated end month	4
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	None - manuscript submitted already

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Improved antibody-antigen modelling by using antibody conformations sampled by MD
ID	A1.9
Software involved	HADDOCK (and input from tasks using GROMACS)
Description	Benchmarking different scenarios for antibody-antigen docking with HADDOCK using antibody conformations sampled by molecular dynamics simulation to measure if these lead to improved docking results
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Reported to EB
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	N.A.
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A1.2 and A1.3
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Docked models will feed into activities A1.4, A1.6 and A1.7
Dependencies on WP1 work?	N.A.
Impact on WP1 work?	Depending on the docking results, changes in MD sampling protocols and selection of conformations might be required.
Dependencies on WP2 work?	N.A.
Impact on WP2 work?	N.A.
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	Best practice coming out of this task should be documented in a antibody-antigen specific tutorial (related to WP3 activities)
Dependencies on project-externals	N.A.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

(e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	
Impact on future users	Optimized protocol for antibody-antigen modelling with HADDOCK depending on the amount of information available and selection schemes to select conformations sampled by MD
Background material/links	Use case description on BioExcel web site
Partner responsible for planning	Utrecht / Alexandre Bonvin, Zuzana Jandova
Partner responsible for executing	Utrecht / Zuzana Jandova
Other partners involved	Stockholm
Estimated required effort (in PM)	6 PMs
Estimated start month	9 (depends on input from A1.2 and 1.3)
Estimated end month	30
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	The accuracy of the docked models will depend on the quality of the conformations sampled by MD.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Demonstration of antibody-antigen modelling on real experimental data
ID	A1.10
Software involved	HADDOCK (and input from tasks using GROMACS)
Description	Applying the optimised antibody-antigen docking protocols coming out of activities A1.8 and A1.9 on real cases with real experimental data to guide the modelling
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Results reported to EB
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	N.A.
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A1.2, A1.3, A1.8, A1.9
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Docked models will feed into activities A1.4, A1.6 and A1.7
Dependencies on WP1 work?	N.A.
Impact on WP1 work?	N.A.
Dependencies on WP2 work?	N.A.
Impact on WP2 work?	N.A.
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	Might provide a demonstration activity for industry
Dependencies on project-externals	The systems to be modelled and associated data will have to come from industrial partners (or possibly targets in blind competitions like

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

(e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	CAPRI)
Impact on future users	Blind demonstration of improved antibody-antigen modelling
Background material/links	Use case description on BioExcel web site
Partner responsible for planning	Utrecht / Alexandre Bonvin, Zuzana Jandova
Partner responsible for executing	Utrecht / Zuzana Jandova
Other partners involved	Stockholm
Estimated required effort (in PM)	3 PMs
Estimated start month	24 (depends on input from A1.2, 1.3, 1.9 and 1.9)
Estimated end month	36
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	No experimental system/data made available from industry. No antibody-antigen target in CAPRI

Use Case 2: High-throughput Modelling of Interactomes

Name of activity	Feasibility analysis of protein-protein interaction energy prediction through all-atom molecular dynamics simulation sampling schemes
ID	A2.1
Software involved	GROMACS
Description	<p>GROMACS meets all necessary requirements to carry out simulations that predict protein-protein binding affinities, however typically sized proteins will require a very efficient simulation setup to perform a sampling that is sufficient to provide a reliable binding affinity estimate. At the moment it is unclear whether or not molecular dynamics simulations, even when using advanced sampling schemes, is suitable for this purpose or whether the required resources would far exceed any available computational resources.</p> <p>The most promising candidates of advanced molecular dynamics simulation sampling methods for binding affinity prediction in this use case are center of mass pulling simulations as well as interaction scaling. If any of these advanced sampling schemes appear suitable however, they will enable massively parallel simulation which then may be favourably used in this use case.</p>
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	A document is made available within BioExcel laying out if reliable protein-protein interaction energy predictions are feasible and what would be the required compute resources.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	N.A.
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	N.A.
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Will determine if all-atom molecular dynamics simulation will be used more extensively in this use case.
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Implementation of advanced molecular dynamics sampling schemes in WP1 will aid this work.
Impact on WP1 work?	Will improve the modelling of interactions in general, include antibody-antigen complexes
Dependencies on WP2 work?	Will require initial docking models to test the approach in real modelling cases, next to experimental structures of complexes
Impact on WP2 work?	Improved modelling of biomolecular complexes in general

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	None
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	None
Impact on future users	Reliable methods for interaction prediction and analysis
Background material/links	
Partner responsible for planning	KTH / Christian Blau
Partner responsible for executing	KTH / Christian Blau
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	0.5
Estimated start month	9
Estimated end month	11
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Improvement in software and methods may alter the finer details of this feasibility study, however we do not expect to come to a very different conclusion within the time-frame of BioExcel. If the analysis shows that protein-protein interaction energy prediction is feasible, more effort might be spent in this use case than planned.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Distinguishing native from non-native docking models by MD
ID	A2.2
Software involved	GROMACS
Description	Scoring functions in protein-protein docking are far from perfect and it is often difficult to distinguish different solutions. This activity is aimed at investigating if relatively short MD simulations of representative models from docking solutions could discriminate between near-native and non-native solutions
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Reported to EB.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	N.A.
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A2.1
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Positive results will also lead to improvements in the modelling of antibody-antigen complexes (Use Case 1)
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Simulations of systems containing non-standard amino-acids and co-factors will depend on a simple mechanism to generate parameters for those for use in GROMACS.
Impact on WP1 work?	Might lead to the development of pipelines between HADDOCK and GROMACS
Dependencies on WP2 work?	Might benefit from solutions developed in WP2
Impact on WP2 work?	Might lead to the development of specific workflows in WP2
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	Will benefit use case 1
Dependencies on	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	
Impact on future users	Improved modelling of biomolecular complexes
Background material/links	None
Partner responsible for planning	Utrecht / Alexandre Bonvin, Zuzana Jandova
Partner responsible for executing	Utrecht / Zuzana Jandova
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	4
Estimated start month	5
Estimated end month	24
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Simulations are too costly to be applied in large scale.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Investigating suitable mechanism of launching a large number of docking simulations as single job on HPC resources
ID	A2.3
Software involved	HADDOCK
Description	Interactome modelling will require running a large number of parallel docking runs in efficient manner on HPC resources. Since not all simulations will require the same amount of time, the job management machinery should allow to free resources once a simulation has completed.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	A suitable job submission mechanism has been defined.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	N.A.
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	N.A.
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Will benefit UC1 by streamlining submission process
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Software development for HADDOCK to decouple the bulk of the computation from the pre- and post-processing steps.
Impact on WP1 work?	None
Dependencies on WP2 work?	Might benefit from solutions developed in WP2
Impact on WP2 work?	None
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	Will benefit use case 1 by streamlining submission process on HPC resources if/when available
Dependencies on	Will depend on the provided batch systems in HPC centra.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	Might also consider Cloud HPC resources (and thus different submission mechanisms)
Impact on future users	Efficient mechanism to run on HPC resources should improve uptake and enable (future) users to make better use of HPC resources
Background material/links	None
Partner responsible for planning	Utrecht / Alexandre Bonvin, Zuzana Jandova
Partner responsible for executing	Utrecht / Zuzana Jandova
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	2
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	10
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Less efficient usage of HPC resources might slightly delay obtaining use case results and/or use provided allocations less efficiently

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Optimize the identification of near-native docking models using machine learning methods
ID	A2.4
Software involved	HADDOCK
Description	For large-scale modelling of interactions, and also in order to couple the docking results with MD simulations in order to assess the validity of the models, it is important to be able to select a limiter number of models, ideally all near-native ones. The current scoring function of HADDOCK is a simple linear combination of energy term. In this activity, using a large set of decoys generated for the docking benchmark version 5, we will revisit scoring using machine learning models (and deep learning possibly) to optimize the selection of near-native models.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Reported in quarterly report
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	N.A.
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	N.A.
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Any improvements in scoring functions will also impact Use Case 1, although we might consider developing antibody-antigen specific scoring functions.
Dependencies on WP1 work?	None
Impact on WP1 work?	Possibly implement the resulting scoring models into HADDOCK
Dependencies on WP2 work?	None
Impact on WP2 work?	None
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	N.A.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	N.A.
Impact on future users	Improved modeling of interactions and better identification of near-native models.
Background material/links	N.A.
Partner responsible for planning	Utrecht / Alexandre Bonvin, Zuzana Jandova
Partner responsible for executing	Utrecht / Zuzana Jandova
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	4
Estimated start month	9
Estimated end month	21
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Resulting model is not generally applicable to a variety of complexes.

Use Case 3: Rational Drug Design

Name of activity	Cancer mutations filtering & identification of pathological mutations
ID	A3.1
Software involved	Cancer mutation databases APIs, PMUT
Description	Identify possible mutations from biological databases related to cancer, and identify the potentially pathological ones using a Machine Learning classifier (PMUT)
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Initial datasets for different workflows ready
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	M1: Cancer mutation databases and PMUT APIs integrated in biobb (PM12) M2: biobb workflow to generate datasets (PM18)
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	N.A.
Impact on another Use Case activity?	A3.2, A3.4, A3.5, A3.6
Dependencies on WP1 work?	N.A.
Impact on WP1 work?	N.A.
Dependencies on WP2 work?	Biobb library use will be explored
Impact on WP2 work?	Dataset generation from biological databases filtering + prediction will be programmed as a workflow
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	N.A.
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the	PMUT

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

project)	
Impact on future users	Users will benefit from dataset generation protocols
Background material/links	http://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/PMut
Partner responsible for planning	BSC / Josep Lluís Gelpí
Partner responsible for executing	BSC / Pau Andrio BSC / Daniele Lezzi
Other partners involved	IRB, NBD
Estimated required effort (in PM)	4
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	18
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	N.A.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Conformational ensembles from protein variants
ID	A3.2
Software involved	BioExcel Building Blocks library (biobb), GROMACS , PyCOMPSs , CWL
Description	Model structures from one (or more than one) variant, perform MD setup and simulations to extract representative conformational ensembles
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Workflow to model structures from one (or more than one) variant and perform MD setup and simulations to extract representative conformational ensembles built and running
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	M1: Updated version of protein mutations workflow (presented in BioExcel) with new functionalities ready (PM12) M2: CWL & PyCOMPSs implementation (PM18)
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	N.A.
Impact on another Use Case activity?	A3.4, A3.5, A3.6, A3.7
Dependencies on WP1 work?	GROMACS code development will improve efficiency of configurational sampling, as well as facilitate simulation setup
Impact on WP1 work?	Feedback from runs in different HPC infrastructures will be used to inform GROMACS development
Dependencies on WP2 work?	BioExcel building blocks, workflow development, CWL description
Impact on WP2 work?	Whole activity will be programmed as a workflow
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	N.A.
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	None
Impact on future	Users will benefit from provided workflows: automated and massive

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

users	parallelization of protein variant modeling + MD setup / running + clustering, ease of installation, running, and modification (thanks to the BioExcel building blocks and workflow library).
Background material/links	Based on the protein mutations workflow presented in BioExcel: https://github.com/bioexcel/biobb_wf_mutations
Partner responsible for planning	IRB / Adam Hospital
Partner responsible for executing	BSC / Pau Andrio BSC / Daniele Lezzi
Other partners involved	BSC, NBD
Estimated required effort (in PM)	4
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	18
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	System complexity will increase difficulty. Tracking of GROMACS use and direct communication with developers (A3.10) will help solving these problems.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Conformational ensembles from small molecules
ID	A3.3
Software involved	BioExcel Building Blocks library (biobb), GROMACS , PyCOMPSs , CWL , OpenBabel , ACPype
Description	Generate representative conformational ensembles from small molecules using biased MD methods
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Workflow built and running
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	M1: biobb Chemistry package to generate 3D structures, add hydrogens and parameterize small molecules (PM12) M2: Biased MD methods integrated in biobb (PM18) M3: CWL & PyCOMPSs implementation (PM24)
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	N.A.
Impact on another Use Case activity?	A3.4, A3.5, A3.8
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Biased MD methods (e.g. REMD) implemented in GROMACS code will improve efficiency of configurational sampling
Impact on WP1 work?	Feedback from runs in different HPC infrastructures will be used to inform GROMACS development
Dependencies on WP2 work?	BioExcel building blocks, workflow development, CWL description
Impact on WP2 work?	Whole activity will be programmed as a workflow
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	N.A.
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	None
Impact on future	Users will benefit from provided workflows: automatic and massive

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

users	parallelization of generation of representative conformational ensembles from small molecules using biased MD methods, easy to install, run, and modify (thanks to the BioExcel building blocks and workflows library).
Background material/links	Based on the work presented in: http://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/webdev/slim/BioactiveCompounds/public
Partner responsible for planning	IRB / Adam Hospital
Partner responsible for executing	BSC / Pau Andrio BSC / Daniele Lezzi
Other partners involved	BSC, NBD
Estimated required effort (in PM)	4
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	24
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Force field parameterization of small ligands is known to be crucial for the quality of the conformational ensemble. Work done by IRB regarding re-parameterizing ligands will help in particularly difficult cases. The quality control of parameters needs to be implemented.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Ensemble Docking
ID	A3.4
Software involved	GROMACS , Autodock , HADDOCK
Description	Massively parallel docking of small molecules conformations (from A3.3) into protein conformations (from A3.2)
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Workflow built and running
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	M1: Updated version of virtual screening workflow (presented in BioExcel) with new functionalities ready (PM12) M2: CWL & PyCOMPSs implementation (PM18)
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A3.2, A3.3
Impact on another Use Case activity?	A3.5, A3.6, A3.7, A3.8
Dependencies on WP1 work?	HADDOCK protein-ligand functionality will be explored
Impact on WP1 work?	HADDOCK modularization can be tested in parallel with the integration in this workflow
Dependencies on WP2 work?	BioExcel building blocks, workflow development, CWL description
Impact on WP2 work?	Whole activity will be programmed as a workflow
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	WP5 pharma-related activities
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	Autodock Vina
Impact on future users	Users will benefit from provided workflows: automatic and massive parallelization of docking small molecules conformations into protein conformations, easiness of installation, running, and modification

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

	(thanks to the BioExcel building blocks and workflow library).
Background material/links	Based on the work done in: https://github.com/bioexcel/virtualsecreening
Partner responsible for planning	IRB / Adam Hospital
Partner responsible for executing	BSC / Pau Andrio BSC / Daniele Lezzi
Other partners involved	BSC, NBD
Estimated required effort (in PM)	5
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	18
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Unsupervised ensemble docking is not always suitable for complex systems. Working with particular test cases will help us to tune the workflow and identify potential issues.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Alchemical free energy calculations of relative ligand binding free energy differences
ID	A3.5
Software involved	GROMACS , pmx
Description	Compute reference binding free energies using GROMACS and pmx, as well as ΔG s for the different protein-ligand complexes.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Workflow built and running
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	M1: basic (protein) pmx functionalities integrated in biobb (with workflow prototype) (PM12) M2: advanced (DNA, small molecules) pmx functionalities integrated in biobb (with workflow prototype) (PM24) M3: CWL & PyCOMPSs implementation (PM36)
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A3.4
Impact on another Use Case activity?	N.A.
Dependencies on WP1 work?	GROMACS and pmx functionality will be explored
Impact on WP1 work?	The functionality of pmx will be enhanced by modularizing ligand modification part. The new functionalities will be tested and feedback will be presented
Dependencies on WP2 work?	BioExcel building blocks, workflow development, CWL description
Impact on WP2 work?	Whole activity will be programmed as a workflow
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	WP5 pharma-related activities
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	N.A.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Impact on future users	Users will benefit from provided workflows: automatic and massive parallelization of reference binding free energies calculations using GROMACS and pmx, as well as ΔG s for the different protein-ligand complexes, easy to install, run, and modify (thanks to the BioExcel building blocks and workflows library).
Background material/links	https://github.com/dseeliger/pmx
Partner responsible for planning	NBD / Yvonne Westermaier
Partner responsible for executing	BSC / Pau Andrio BSC / Daniele Lezzi
Other partners involved	BSC, NB, MPG / Vytautas Gapsys
Estimated required effort (in PM)	6
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	36
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	The accuracy of the free energy calculations depends highly on the starting models and might be affected by the automatic high-throughput procedures. Working with particular test cases will help us to tune the workflow and identify potential issues.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Molecular Dynamics trajectories analyses
ID	A3.6
Software involved	GROMACS , AmberTools , CMIP , TRAPP
Description	Building of a set of interesting analyses from MD trajectories, mainly related to changes on the surface of the protein: interfaces, cavities, pockets, energy grids, etc.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Workflow integrating the set of analysis built and running
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	M1: General AmberTools analysis integrated in biobb (cpptraj) (PM12) M2: Protein surface analysis (energy grids, pockets, interfaces, cavities, etc.) analysis integrated in biobb (PM24) M3: CWL & PyCOMPSs implementation (PM36)
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A3.2, A3.4
Impact on another Use Case activity?	A3.7
Dependencies on WP1 work?	GROMACS analysis tools functionality will be explored
Impact on WP1 work?	GROMACS analysis tools feedback will be presented
Dependencies on WP2 work?	BioExcel building blocks, workflow development, CWL description
Impact on WP2 work?	Analysis will be implemented as building blocks, and different workflows with a chosen set of analysis will be built from them
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	WP5 pharma-related activities
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma	AmberTools, TRAPP

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

companies, software not developed in the project)	
Impact on future users	Users will benefit from provided workflows: automated and massive parallelization of a set of useful analyses from MD trajectories, easiness of installation, running, and modification (thanks to the BioExcel building blocks and workflow library).
Background material/links	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/11746690 https://trapp.h-its.org/ http://ambermd.org/AmberTools.php
Partner responsible for planning	IRB / Adam Hospital
Partner responsible for executing	BSC / Pau Andrio BSC / Daniele Lezzi
Other partners involved	BSC, NBD
Estimated required effort (in PM)	4
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	36
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	N.A.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Molecular Dynamics trajectories storage
ID	A3.7
Software involved	N.A.
Description	MD trajectories storage in FAIR MD databases (IRB based), programmatically accessible by APIs, according to DMP presented in D3.2
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	MD trajectories and analyses available on-line
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	M1: First dataset of MD Trajectories available from the IRB MD database prototype (PM18) M2: Final dataset of MD Trajectories available from the IRB MD database (PM36)
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A3.2, A3.4, A3.6
Impact on another Use Case activity?	N.A.
Dependencies on WP1 work?	N.A.
Impact on WP1 work?	N.A.
Dependencies on WP2 work?	N.A.
Impact on WP2 work?	N.A.
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	ELIXIR interoperability, FAIR databases
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	N.A.
Impact on future users	Users will benefit from freely available on-line MD trajectories, with all the associated metadata

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Background material/links	Based on databases such as: https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/BigNASim/
Partner responsible for planning	IRB / Adam Hospital
Partner responsible for executing	IRB / Adam Hospital IRB / Aurélien Luciani
Other partners involved	BSC, NBD
Estimated required effort (in PM)	4
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	36
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	MD trajectories generate huge amounts of data, and the database infrastructure should be prepared to deal with this, which is not straightforward. Experience gained with the two databases built by IRB (MoDEL, BigNASim) will help during the process. NoSQL databases and a robust and suitable infrastructure (Starlife) will be used.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Peptide mutational scans
ID	A3.8
Software involved	pmx, BioExcel building blocks
Description	Peptide mutational scans based on a pre-generated amino acid library.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Workflow for the peptide scan built and running
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	M1: First workflow prototype including a peptide mutational scan using pmx (PM24) M2: CWL & PyCOMPSs implementation (PM36)
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A3.3, A3.5
Impact on another Use Case activity?	N.A.
Dependencies on WP1 work?	pmx
Impact on WP1 work?	N.A.
Dependencies on WP2 work?	BioExcel building blocks, workflow development, CWL description
Impact on WP2 work?	Analysis will be implemented as building blocks, and different workflows with a chosen set of analysis will be built from them
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	WP5 pharma-related activities
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	N.A.
Impact on future users	Users will benefit from provided workflows: automated and massive parallelization of peptide mutational scans based on a pre-generated amino acid library, easiness of installation, running, and modification

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

	(thanks to the BioExcel building blocks and workflow library).
Background material/links	N.A.
Partner responsible for planning	NBD / Yvonne Westermaier
Partner responsible for executing	BSC / Pau Andrio BSC / Daniele Lezzi
Other partners involved	IRB
Estimated required effort (in PM)	4
Estimated start month	18
Estimated end month	36
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	As in A3.5, the accuracy of the free energy calculations highly depends upon the starting models and might be affected by automatic high-throughput procedures. Working with particular test cases will help us to tune the workflow and identify potential issues.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	High Performance Data Analytics
ID	A3.9
Software involved	PyCOMPSs , Dislib
Description	HPDA methods will be applied together with HPC calculations thanks to the dislib library implemented in PyCOMPSs.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	HPDA-HPC combining workflow built and running
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	M1: First workflow prototype including an HPDA-HPC combined analysis using dislib (PM24) M2: Machine learning workflow for efficient drug design workflow (PM36)
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A3.4, A3.5, A3.6
Impact on another Use Case activity?	N.A.
Dependencies on WP1 work?	N.A.
Impact on WP1 work?	N.A.
Dependencies on WP2 work?	BioExcel building blocks, workflow development, CWL description
Impact on WP2 work?	HPDA & HPC alignment
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	N.A.
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	N.A.
Impact on future users	Users will benefit from provided workflows: automated and massive parallelization of HPDA methods coupled to HPC.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Background material/links	https://www.bsc.es/ca/research-and-development/software-and-apps/software-list/dislib/documentation
Partner responsible for planning	BSC / Rosa M Badia
Partner responsible for executing	BSC / Pau Andrio BSC / Daniele Lezzi
Other partners involved	IRB, NBD
Estimated required effort (in PM)	5
Estimated start month	18
Estimated end month	36
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	HPDA addresses Machine Learning-related issues: underfitting, overfitting, choosing/finding the right model, etc. Combining HPDA with HPC in HT pipelines (unsupervised) is extremely risky. Again, working with particular test cases will help us to tune the workflow/s and identify potential issues.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Enabling advanced use of GROMACS, improve usability & implement advanced functionality within the use case
ID	A3.10
Software involved	GROMACS
Description	The whole use case is extremely dependent on GROMACS package. Efficient and advanced use of it will have a great impact on the final result. Pre-processing steps, clustering algorithms, or enhanced sampling methods are processes requiring specific fine-tuning.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Fine-tuned and improved workflows will be developed during the whole use case lifetime
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	N.A.
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	N.A.
Impact on another Use Case activity?	A3.2, A3.3, A3.4, A3.5, A3.6
Dependencies on WP1 work?	A python API to GROMACS would facilitate these tasks.
Impact on WP1 work?	GROMACS feedback on multiple functionalities: pre-processing, simulation, enhanced sampling and analysis
Dependencies on WP2 work?	N.A.
Impact on WP2 work?	Increase efficiency and robustness in BioExcel building blocks, and workflows built from them
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	WP1 GROMACS development
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Impact on future users	Users will benefit from provided building blocks, and workflows that have been tested and improved by the GROMACS developers themselves
Background material/links	N.A.
Partner responsible for planning	KTH / Christian Blau
Partner responsible for executing	KTH / Paul Bauer
Other partners involved	IRB, BSC
Estimated required effort (in PM)	4
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	36
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Reaching a balance between the level of integration of GROMACS advanced functionalities and the easiness of use of the BioExcel building blocks and workflows might be difficult to achieve.

Use Case 4: Electronic Interaction Phenomena

Name of activity	Inquiring needs and document interface to apply forces from QM simulations during molecular dynamics simulation
ID	A4.1
Software involved	GROMACS / CP2K
Description	GROMACS provides basic, though dated infrastructure to QM/MM simulations. Support for CP2K is lacking, though under development. The GROMACS team in Stockholm is in contact with JYU and JUELICH to aid implementing an interface between GROMACS and CP2K.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Documented the needs of the use case researchers for efficiently applying forces during QM/MM simulations.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	None
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	None
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Will aid to improve and stabilize the software used during the use case.
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Further development on GROMACS to provide external data and forces to simulations will aid outlining a QM interface.
Impact on WP1 work?	Helps guide GROMACS development work.
Dependencies on WP2 work?	None
Impact on WP2 work?	None
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	None
Impact on future users	QM/MM simulation setup will be easier
Background material/links	
Partner responsible for planning	KTH / Christian Blau
Partner responsible for executing	KTH / Christian Blau
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	1
Estimated start month	10
Estimated end month	22
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	The acquired needs and interface during the use case research need to be up to date with the ongoing software development process. This mitigated by a steady communication flow between GROMACS development team and use case researchers as well as training the use case researchers in the issue management system that is used during software development.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Prepare fluorescent proteins and mutants models for simulation
ID	A4.2
Software involved	GROMACS pre-processing tools, model building tools
Description	Models for molecular dynamics, free energy perturbation and QM/MM simulations will be prepared. Depending on the availability and completeness of crystal structures of each particular modification of protein it could take additional efforts to produce stable structures of mutants, solvate and equilibrated them. This also includes system setup for proteins dimers.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Stable structure of the proteins during equilibration simulations
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	None
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	None
Impact on another Use Case activity?	This will be a starting point for all further calculations performed in Use-Case 4
Dependencies on WP1 work?	No dependencies
Impact on WP1 work?	None
Dependencies on WP2 work?	Usage of workflows from WP2 could potentially improve automatization of this step
Impact on WP2 work?	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	None
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	Some of the crystal structures could be provided by our collaborators in KU Leuven
Impact on future users	This step will provide future user with a demonstration of structure preparation and processing to make models of fluorescent proteins for simulations.
Background material/links	
Partner responsible for planning	JYU
Partner responsible for executing	JYU
Other partners involved	N.A.
Estimated required effort (in PM)	3
Estimated start month	3
Estimated end month	12
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Depending on the availability of high-quality structures of mutants it might take an additional time to setup all of them.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Extensive sampling of fluorescent proteins conformations using classical molecular dynamics
ID	A4.3
Software involved	GROMACS
Description	Perform extensive sampling of possible conformations of each fluorescent protein and their mutants. This will be done by producing large molecular dynamics trajectories with GROMACS and further analysis of them. At the later stages, to improve sampling, enhanced techniques could be used.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Whenever activities A4.4-A4.6 will have enough structures.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	None
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A4.2
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Provides input structures for A4.4-A4.6
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Improvements in GROMACS code will facilitate sampling.
Impact on WP1 work?	None
Dependencies on WP2 work?	Could use workflows from WP2 for automatization at later stages
Impact on WP2 work?	Provides systems for testing workflows
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	N.A.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	None
Impact on future users	Provides future users with simulation protocols
Background material/links	N.A.
Partner responsible for planning	JYU
Partner responsible for executing	JYU
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	6
Estimated start month	6
Estimated end month	24
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Potential difficulties with availability of computing resources.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Free energy simulations of folding and dimerization of different fluorescent proteins mutants.
ID	A4.4
Software involved	GROMACS, pymacs
Description	Perform free energy perturbation simulations using GROMACS to calculate folding and dimerization free energies of different fluorescent proteins and their mutants. These free energies could be related to the experimental observations and measurements of stability and dimerization constants.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Calculated free energies will be confirmed by comparison with experimental data.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	None
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A4.2, A4.3
Impact on another Use Case activity?	None
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Improvements in GROMACS free energy code.
Impact on WP1 work?	we will use Pymacs and provide user feedback
Dependencies on WP2 work?	Could use workflows from WP2 for automatization at later stages
Impact on WP2 work?	Provides systems for testing workflows
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	N.A.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	Experimental data to compare will be provided by our collaborators in KU Leuven
Impact on future users	Provides future users with simulation protocols
Background material/links	N.A.
Partner responsible for planning	JYU
Partner responsible for executing	JYU
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	6
Estimated start month	8
Estimated end month	14
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Potential difficulties with availability of computing resources. Difficulties with experimental measurements.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Calculation of isomerization profiles of chromophores in protein environments
ID	A4.5
Software involved	GROMACS, CP2K
Description	Calculations of the chromophore isomerization profiles in the different mutants. These will allow us to predict efficiency of switching between fluorescent and dark states of the chosen proteins and mutants. Simulations will be performed using different structures provided by A4.3 and new QMMM interface between GROMACS and CP2K developed in WP1
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Simulations will be published and tutorial will be made on the basis of them.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	None
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A4.3
Impact on another Use Case activity?	None
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Will be performed using new QMMM interface between GROMACS and CP2K
Impact on WP1 work?	Will provide test and tutorial case for GROMACS/CP2K interface
Dependencies on WP2 work?	None
Impact on WP2 work?	None
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	N.A.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	Some experimental data will be provided by our external collaborators
Impact on future users	Provides future users with simulation protocols
Background material/links	
Partner responsible for planning	JYU
Partner responsible for executing	JYU
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	9
Estimated start month	12
Estimated end month	24
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	This activity is highly dependent of the availability of the new GROMACS/CP2K QMMM interface

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Modelling of spectral properties of fluorescent proteins and their mutants
ID	A4.6
Software involved	GROMACS, CP2K
Description	Calculations of absorption and fluorescence spectra will be performed in conformations produced by A4.3 using new QMMM interface between GROMACS and CP2K. After that spectra will be convolved and predictivity of models will be established in comparison to experimentally measured spectra.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Spectra simulations will be published and tutorial will be made.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	None
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A4.3
Impact on another Use Case activity?	None
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Will be performed using new QMMM interface between GROMACS and CP2K
Impact on WP1 work?	Will provide test and tutorial case for GROMACS/CP2K interface
Dependencies on WP2 work?	None
Impact on WP2 work?	None
Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	N.A.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	Experimental spectra data will be provided by our collaborators
Impact on future users	Provides future users with simulation protocols
Background material/links	N.A.
Partner responsible for planning	JYU
Partner responsible for executing	JYU
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	6
Estimated start month	12
Estimated end month	24
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	This activity is highly dependent on the availability of the new GROMACS/CP2K QMMM interface

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Prepare the beta-lactoglobulin protein models for molecular dynamics simulations
ID	A4.7
Software involved	GROMACS pre-processing tools, model building tools
Description	The models with the beta-lactoglobulin protein with and without solvent shell will be prepared. Equilibration at force-field level in water and in vacuo will be performed. Clustering analysis of the two equilibrated trajectories will be performed in order to identify structures which can be used for the further investigation of proton transport.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	Stable structure of the proteins during equilibration simulations and representative cluster conformations
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	Equilibrated representative structures for the case in vacuum, are going to be obtained at M14
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	None
Impact on another Use Case activity?	This will be a starting point for the further calculations on beta-lactoglobulin in Use-Case 4
Dependencies on WP1 work?	No dependencies
Impact on WP1 work?	None
Dependencies on WP2 work?	None
Impact on WP2 work?	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	None
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	None
Impact on future users	This step will provide future users with a protocol for the structure preparation and clustering analysis in the investigation of the impact of proton transport in ESI/IM-MS experiments.
Background material/links	Arcella A., J. Dreyer, E. Ippoliti, I. Ivani, G. Portella, V. Gabelica, P. Carloni, M. Orozco, Structure and Dynamics of Oligonucleotides in the Gas Phase, <i>Angewandte Chemie</i> 2015. 127(2): p. 477–481. https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25417598
Partner responsible for planning	JUELICH
Partner responsible for executing	JUELICH
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	3
Estimated start month	13
Estimated end month	15
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Depending on the availability of high-quality structures of beta-lactamglobulin protein it might take an additional time to identify the relevant structures for the proton transport investigation.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	QM and QM/MM investigation of proton transport in beta-lactamglobulin protein by CPMD and MiMiC interface
ID	A4.8
Software involved	CPMD and MiMiC interface
Description	Starting from the representative structures identified in activity A4.7, full QM molecular dynamics simulations for the in vacuo systems and QM/MM molecular dynamics simulations for the solvated system will be performed by CPMD and CPMD combined with the MiMiC interface, respectively.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	When we get the analysis of the comparison of the proton transport occurrence between the in vacuo and solvated system.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	First the full QM case of the in vacuo systems will be obtained. This should be completed within M19.
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A4.7
Impact on another Use Case activity?	Reference data for A4.9
Dependencies on WP1 work?	None
Impact on WP1 work?	None
Dependencies on WP2 work?	None
Impact on WP2 work?	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	None
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	CPMD and MiMiC who are not developed in BioExcel 2.
Impact on future users	Provides future users with simulation protocols in the investigation of the impact of proton transport in ESI/IM-MS experiments.
Background material/links	Arcella A., J. Dreyer, E. Ippoliti, I. Ivani, G. Portella, V. Gabelica, P. Carloni, M. Orozco, Structure and Dynamics of Oligonucleotides in the Gas Phase, <i>Angewandte Chemie</i> 2015. 127(2): p. 477–481. https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25417598
Partner responsible for planning	JUELICH
Partner responsible for executing	JUELICH
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	0
Estimated start month	16
Estimated end month	24
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Potential difficulties with availability of computing resources since this is a computational demanding activity. The team has a large experience in collecting grants for computational time on the largest European supercomputing centers and proposals for computational time devoted to this activity will be submitted well in advance (M13).

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	QM and QM/MM investigation of proton transport in beta-lactamglobulin protein by CP2K and CP2K/GROMACS QM/MM interface
ID	A4.9
Software involved	CP2K and CP2K/GROMACS QM/MM interface
Description	Starting from the representative structures identified in activity A4.7, full QM molecular dynamics simulations for the in vacuo systems and QM/MM molecular dynamics simulations for the solvated system will be performed by CP2K and CP2K/GROMACS QM/MM interface, respectively. Comparison with the results obtained in activity A4.8 will be done.
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	When we get the analysis of the comparison of the proton transport occurrence between the in vacuo and solvated system with the new software.
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	First the full QM case of the in vacuo systems will be obtained. This should be completed within M29.
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	A4.7
Impact on another Use Case activity?	None
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Availability of CP2K/GROMACS QM/MM interface
Impact on WP1 work?	User feedback for the new interface
Dependencies on WP2 work?	None
Impact on WP2 work?	None

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	None
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	None
Impact on future users	Provides future users with simulation protocols in the investigation of the impact of proton transport in ESI/IM-MS experiments.
Background material/links	Arcella A., J. Dreyer, E. Ippoliti, I. Ivani, G. Portella, V. Gabelica, P. Carloni, M. Orozco, Structure and Dynamics of Oligonucleotides in the Gas Phase, <i>Angewandte Chemie</i> 2015. 127(2): p. 477–481. https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25417598
Partner responsible for planning	JUELICH
Partner responsible for executing	JUELICH
Other partners involved	None
Estimated required effort (in PM)	7
Estimated start month	25
Estimated end month	36
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Potential difficulties with availability of computing resources since this is a computational demanding activity. The team has a large experience in collecting grants for computational time on the largest European supercomputing centers and proposals for computational time devoted to this activity will be submitted in advance (M24).

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Name of activity	Supporting massively parallel QM/MM simulations of protein dynamics and fluorescent proteins
ID	A4.10
Software involved	CP2K and CP2K/GROMACS QM/MM interface
Description	Supporting massively parallel hybrid QM/MM simulations using the BioExcel QM/MM interface in order to illustrate scaling, performance, and efficiency of large-scale prediction of proton and residue dynamics and fluorescent proteins, and showing how large QM regions (several hundred atoms) require studies on pre-Exascale resources
How will we know when it is done? (Final milestone)	We will have obtained scaling runs of both use case problems for large QM regions, explored optimisations, shown reasonable efficiency, and arrived at recommendations for best practice
Intermediate milestone(s), including expected completion PM	Initial results from large-scale runs expected around PM 24.
Dependency on another Use Case activity?	4.5, 4.6, 4.9
Impact on another Use Case activity?	4.5, 4.6, 4.9
Dependencies on WP1 work?	Availability of CP2K/GROMACS QM/MM interface
Impact on WP1 work?	It is possible that findings as part of this activity will feed back to the QM/MM work in WP1, however that is not its main aim as effort to do this exists within WP1
Dependencies on WP2 work?	N.A.
Impact on WP2 work?	N.A.

D3.1 – Use Case Work Plans

Connections with any other project tasks or activities?	Results and experience gained in this activity could feed into the generation of a relevant best practice guide or tutorial as part of T3.3 (In-Depth Support) or T3.4 (Standards & Best Practice)
Dependencies on project-externals (e.g. pharma companies, software not developed in the project)	None
Impact on future users	The results of this activity should help demonstrate the value of BioExcel's work in this area to (potential) users and promote uptake. Experience gained in this activity should aid future users in making use of the QM/MM functionality developed and apply it to their own problems.
Background material/links	N.A.
Partner responsible for planning	UEDIN, JYU, JUELICH
Partner responsible for executing	UEDIN
Other partners involved	JYU, JUELICH
Estimated required effort (in PM)	7
Estimated start month	12
Estimated end month	36
Risks, impacts, and risk mitigation	Relies on availability of QM/MM functionality